

ECONOMIC ANALYSIS OF DEVELOPMENT OF INVESTMENT PROJECTS AND ITS MANAGEMENT

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ABSTRACT

Development of the economy of Uzbekistan based on new criteria is closely related to the implementation of an active investment policy, and this is one of the most important conditions of the reform strategy. In this regard, one of the methods of managing the attraction of foreign investments, including direct investments, to the country's economy is to further increase the investment attractiveness of the country and its regions.

Keywords: *economy, investment, project, financing, private sector, non-profit partner, investment, private capital, credit*

INTRODUCTION

The investment attractiveness of Uzbekistan is characterized by the growth of the country's economy, the level of development of entrepreneurship, the development of regional markets, the availability of various investment objects, natural resources and highly qualified personnel, protection and support system.

The methods and approaches for assessing the attractiveness of the investment environment proposed in the scientific works of foreign and our country's scientists are important in the comparative assessment of the level of development of regions, to collect information about their indicators and to determine the options for rating points for them. In view of this, in order to ensure the high objectivity of the evaluation by scoring, taking into account the rating criteria and the individual indicators that reflect them, we have improved the rating evaluation of the investment attractiveness of the

regions of Uzbekistan based on statistical data based on the rating score. In this study, we used the method presented in the works, which is practically simple and reliable.

In order to use internal and external sources of financing investment projects in Uzbekistan, it is necessary to ensure the legal and economic foundations of this field, to study its undiscovered and unexplored aspects and to put them into practice. Management of investment projects in the conditions of Uzbekistan is complicated by the need to take into account many variable factors. Therefore, the effectiveness of investment projects should be evaluated by several criteria and several methods.

METHODS

The state independence of Uzbekistan opened a new page in the development of the national economy. There have been positive changes in networks and inter-network proportions, new networks have been created, and the number of joint ventures is growing. Huge investments were attracted to economic growth. Large-scale investments mobilized in the fuel and energy complex, mechanical engineering, metallurgy, chemical complex, light industry, food and processing sectors of industry are related to the establishment of import-substituting production and the development of new types of products. It has been. In recent years, investments in the transport complex, communications, social sphere, including the sphere of education, have been increasing more and more. Such structural changes create opportunities to enter the world economy and achieve sustainable growth of the country's economy.

For ease of analysis and synthesis of projects, different management systems can be classified on different bases. Below is a set of derived classification systems. But it should be remembered that this system is not the only system. The type of project (according to the main areas of activity of the implemented project) will be organizational, economic, social and mixed.

The class of the project (according to the structure and system of the project and its field of study) is divided into mono-project, multi-project, multi-project. Monoproject is a separate project of different type, construction and size. A multi-

project is a complex project consisting of several mono-projects and requiring a multi-project management application. Myegaloyiha is the fields of education and hakoza. Targeted development programs include a number of mono- and multi-projects.

Project scale - (by project size, number of participants and level of environmental impact): small projects, medium projects, large projects, very large projects. This distribution of projects is very conditional. The scope of the project can be seen in a clearer form. Interstate, international, national interregional and regional, intersectoral and intersectoral, cooperative, organizational projects.

In accordance with the classification and divisions of projects, several features and typical conditions can be distinguished that distinguish projects from each other.

The field of science of the project is divided into several types. Investment projects usually include projects that require investments, the main purpose of which is the production of basic funds, i.e. renewal.

RESULTS

Financing is definitely required for the implementation of projects developed for the development of the country's economy. It should be noted that it is no secret that most of the investments are being directed to the production sectors in the context of modernization of the current economy. Preparation and analysis of investments directed to the project of development of production enterprises mainly depends on the goals of the enterprise, that is, what it wants to achieve with the help of investment. From this point of view, investment projects can be divided into the following groups:

- investment projects aimed at increasing economic efficiency. The main goal of such projects is to create conditions for reducing the costs of enterprises based on the replacement of equipment, improvement of the skills of employees, relocation of production facilities to efficient areas.

- investment projects to expand production. The purpose of such investment projects is to expand the possibilities of production of goods for previously formed markets at the expense of existing capacities.

- investment projects to create new productions. Such projects allow to create new types of goods and services that have not been produced before, or to enter new markets by improving the quality of previously produced goods.

- projects designed to meet the requirements of state management agencies, i.e., projects designed to meet the requirements of ecology and product standards. This classification of investment projects is based on the fact that the level of risk is different.

From the above, the first and fourth types of investment projects have a low level of risk, and the other two have a high level of risk. It should be noted that the production of a product previously unknown in the market and the investment cost for capturing new markets require a large risk. Therefore, investments of the third group are investments with the highest risk.

Investments in production expansion have lower risk than investments in new production. At the moment, the investments made to increase efficiency are aimed at improving the quality of goods already accepted by the market and reducing their cost, so the level of risk in them is much lower than that of investments of the second and third groups. Similarly, the level of risk of investments spent on meeting the requirements of government agencies is considered to be much smaller. The level of risk of investments in projects also depends on the project environment, and the project environment plays an important role in its financing.

DISCUSSION

Based on the company's development strategy, the management summarizes the special requirements of specialists. Therefore, first it is necessary to determine whether there is a possibility to improve the social and economic indicators of the enterprise or industry with the help of investment. After that, it is necessary to deeply study the ideas about investment and create a business plan based on this. If this plan arouses the interest of investors and customers, the work should be continued in the next stages.

This direction consists of an in-depth analysis of the business plan and its economic and financial evaluation.

When accepting an investment project, the ratio of its usefulness and costs is taken into account. The profitability of an investment is measured by the expected net profit from its use, and the investor hopes to receive it. Expenses are the amount of interest spent on attracting debt funds.

Naturally, the investor directs his capital to projects that provide an increase in the expected rate of net profit from the amount of interest paid for borrowed funds. Therefore, the rate of expected net profit and the amount of interest paid are the two main factors that determine the costs of an investment. In addition, other factors are involved in the acceptance of an investment project, including: the type of investment, the cost of the investment project, the presence of many similar projects, limited financial resources, risk, etc.

The main reason for the private sector's desire to participate in these areas is the possibility of increasing the efficiency of the facilities in the conditions where the managers are personally responsible. In cases where private investors are successfully involved in household services, there is also a certain interest in the expansion of opportunities to acquire financial resources.

Expediency of the budget funds provided for in the conclusions of the preliminary feasibility study or calculation of the Ministry of Economy and Finance, which envisages cutting off the deficit of funds for the payment of loans of social importance at the expense of the budget funds (non-compliance) and volumes, including conclusions on the granting of tax benefits, should be available.

The document on the initial feasibility study or calculation approval shall include the name of the project, its initiator, the limited cost of construction (including the cost of importing technological and other equipment), the calculated capacity of the object (the annual volume of the produced product and nomenclature), as well as indicators of economic efficiency, including information on the volume of exports.

CONCLUSION

Based on the approved preliminary feasibility study or calculation parameters of the project, including the limited limits of financing by types of expenses, by the project initiator, in the prescribed manner:

- funding sources are defined and agreed upon;
- Tender documents will be developed to identify contractors and suppliers of technological equipment to be purchased under the project.

Review and preparation of projects implemented with the involvement of debt funds from international financial and economic institutions and foreign government financial organizations is carried out in two stages: In the first stage, the project initiators are the "Davarkhitektkurilis" committee, the Ministry of Economy and Finance and the Ministry of Foreign Affairs to the Ministry of Economic Relations, Investments and Trade on the need to implement the project, prepared on the basis of the reports of the pre-assessment missions of the International Financial and Economic Institutions or Foreign Government Financial Organizations, including the initial estimate of the project cost and the amount of borrowed funds make suggestions

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